

FORMATION OF CULTURE OF INFORMATION EXCHANGE AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY

Rakhimova Shakhnoza Anvarovna

Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)
in Sociological Sciences, Tashkent University of Information
Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

Email: Shaxnoz10@mail.ru

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To fully address the actual problems of youth, it is necessary to have a comprehensive and thorough study of the actual problems of young people through the methods of social sciences. At the same time, studying the interests of young people should be a continuous process, not a mere action. It is necessary to monitor the progress of the youth in step by step. It is possible to conclude about current trends in youth development, their future challenges and plans. In this article, a sociological survey was conducted in the higher education institutions of Uzbekistan on the theme "Formation of culture of information exchange among young people in the information society (for example, students in higher education institutions)" to study the level of formation of the culture of information exchange in our society.

The research was conducted in participation of 3 institutes as the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, and 4 universities as Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, Tashkent State Agrarian University, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages and 5 branches of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad Al-Khorezmi in Samarkand, Fergana, Urgench, Nukus and Karshi by involving students 18 to 33 years old.

Digital statistics on the students of higher education institutions involved in sociological research in Tashkent

No	Higher Education Institution	Total number of students	Male	Female	Including				Average index of students involved in research
					1st Year	2nd Year	3rd Year	4th Year	

1	Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute	99	56	43	99	0	0	0	18-27
2	Uzbekistan State Institute of Art and Culture	97	64	33	69	12	16	0	18-31
3	Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers	118	92	26	5	69	43	1	18-32
4	Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Mukhammad Al-Khorezmi	100	52	48	16	18	21	45	18-27
5	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi	102	12	90	61	0	27	14	18-33
6	Tashkent State Agrarian University	100	78	22	40	19	33	8	19-28
7	Uzbekistan State World Languages University	99	25	74	44	45	8	2	18-23
Total:		715	379	336	334	163	148	70	

Digital statistics on the students of higher education institutions involved in sociological surveys in the regions

N o	Higher Education Institution	Total number of student	Ma le	Fema le	Including				Average age index of students
					1 st Yea r	2 nd Yea r	3 rd Yea r	4 th Yea r	

		s								involved in research
1	TUIT Fergana Branch	100	85	15	47	34	19	0		18-27
2	TUIT Urgench Branch	100	69	31	50	14	28	8		19-28
3	TUIT Nukus Branch	100	68	32	51	49	0	0		18-27
4	TUIT Samarkand Branch	100	91	9	0	4	56	40		18-27
5	TUIT Karshi Branch	100	71	29	28	23	24	25		19-30
Total:		500	384	116	176	124	127	73		

1400 questionnaires for the survey were distributed through the survey methodology, based on the total number of students studying at higher education institutions in Tashkent and regions.

Students who participated in the survey responded to the first question in our questionnaire. Dear Respondent, what do you think the concept of information means? 28% respondents described it as a systematic casting of events, 22% of respondents described as any significant information, 16% respondents described it as an information on something, 22% respondents described it as information necessary in human activities, 11% respondents described it as information relayed through mass media, 1% respondents limited with a response as it is difficult to answer this question.

Summarizing the answers above, we can see that the level of information awareness is almost positive. At the same time, this factor influences the ability of people to fully understand and accept information. Everybody knows that the information has a serious impact on the psycho-emotional state of the person, so it is essential that the rules of dissemination and use of information should be constantly improved with the modernization of the society. In addition, new forms of information use may be used in the context of the use of information, in which the impact of the group's internal environment and the impact of its influence can be used as a tool for information dissemination among other members of the group.

Respondents' answers to the question "Please show the source of information" in the questionnaire were as follows: 21% respondents marked TV, 13% respondents showed print media sources (books, newspapers, magazines), 7% respondents marked radio, 28% respondents marked internet, 6% respondents marked people around, 7% respondents marked social media (such as Facebook, Twitter, etc.), 8% respondents marked messengers (Telegram, WhatsApp, etc.) and 10% respondents marked library.

This was mainly due to the fact that our survey was conducted among generations of 18-33 years old. It is worth noting that the use of information and information through the Internet is widely used among young people. Another interesting aspect is that only 6% of respondents said that people around them were the main sources of information for them. This indicates that individuals are actively seeking information or information.

Respondents' answers to the question "Do you share the information you have with your friends, close people or others around you?" were as follows: 41% respondents answered "Yes", of course, 3% respondents answered "No", 55% respondents "Sometimes, based on what information it is", 1% of respondents answered "It is difficult to answer".

From the above answers, we can see that the half of respondents feel that they are living in an information-sharing environment and that this process is often related to their psycho-social attributes. Respondents' answers to the question "How Do You Arrange Your Free Time?" were as follows: 46% respondents - Internet, 36% - work during free time, 14% respondents - in libraries, 4% respondents - in leisure, and 1% - no free time.

We are aware that organizing and conducting leisure activities of young people is done exclusively out of educational and cultural institutions. The survey found that most of the respondents spent their free time surfing the Internet. The Internet is a tool that influences the minds of young people. There are many positive aspects of the Internet, but it does have negative sides as well. Unfortunately, all this time is not just built on ethical values.

To the question, "Do you have membership at the Information Resource Center (library)? 83% of the respondents said "Yes, of course", and 17% of respondents said "No". As we were not fully satisfied with this question, an expert interview was held. This is because the 1st year students enrolled in higher education institutions are registered at information resource centers in compulsory manner. This does not mean that 83% of young people use the

information resource centers. The expert survey showed that 60% of students use information resource centers.

To the question “What purposes do you use Information Resource Center if you are a member?”, 35% of respondents answered “To receive reliable information”, 18% respondents answered “I visit mainly for spiritual leisure, 5% of respondents - “I use for retrospective data”, 7% respondents - “There is a high level of service quality”, 31% respondents - “I can always find the information I look for”, 4% respondents - “I don’t not know, never thought about it before”.

35% of our respondents are answering that they receive reliable information and 31% of the respondents have always been able to find the information there and thus they are showing higher percentages. It is clear from their answers that the funding of the information resource centers of higher education institutions is well-established, and it is important for students to find reliable information in the information library facilities.

Dear respondent, what kind of world information resources do you use? 17% respondents - EBSCO, 61% respondents - eLibrary, 7% respondents - JSTOR, 7% respondents - ProQues, 4% respondents - Emerald, and 4% respondents - Springer.

In the recent years, the use of global information resources has been rarely used. World news resources are scientific and educational electronic resources of leading world companies and publishers, which use six licensed information resources in the field of science and education. They make a great contribution to the development of business and business. Today, the National Library named after Alisher Navoi consists of local EBSCO, eLibrary, JSTOR, ProQues, Emerald and Springer. These informational resources open up new opportunities for students to support research and educational activities. The electronic resources provided are available in various fields of science and education: medicine. agriculture, sociology, library science, financial management and information technology. In addition, students can use not only online information resources of foreign scientific education but also in reading rooms of information-library facilities, as well as through their web-sites.

Today, our young people, who are able to freely communicate in some foreign languages, are using the online information resources of scientific education as the first pleasant fruit of all our efforts in the field of education. We can add to the positive aspects of the exchange of information when young people are educated, their rational use of scientifically-educational resources.

To the question, “Is the culture of communication in the Internet formed in Uzbekistan?”, 37% respondents answered “Yes”, 30% respondents answered “No, but this is a serious question”, 30% respondents answered “No, it is in the process of being formed”, 3% respondents answered “No, there is no need”. In conclusion, the results of the research show that the culture of information exchange among the youth of the country is satisfactory in the process of modernization of the society. Considering the fact that Sociological Research was conducted among students of higher education institutions, it is necessary that important conclusions, recommendations are developed and put into practice in real life.

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